

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: ENDALE****FIRST NAME: GULELAT****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 0%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Writing Academic Essay (EUCLID 2021, 6-14)
2. Punctuation (EUCLID 2021, 15-23)
3. American and British English (EUCLID 2021, 24-32)
4. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 33-41)
5. Style Guide (EUCLID 2021, 40-42)

WRITING ACADEMIC ESSAY

1) INTRODUCTION

This response paper is prepared based on reading and interaction with a coursepack on International Academic Writing which was prepared by Professor Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr. Kabiru Gulma (EUCLID 2021). This response paper summarizes the course material studied in this section and the student's reaction to the course pack in the next section.

The course pack introduces the basics of academic and professional paper writing, including essential steps in writing academic essays and the rules of thumb for writing academic essays. It covers essential topics such as proper use of punctuation marks and examples of their use, American and British English, plagiarism, writing style, and Chicago style. The course pack also provides standard Latin abbreviations and expressions used by technical communicators (EUCLID 2021, 58-64) and sample correction to response paper (EUCLID 2021, 66).

2) ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

This section presents my understanding and reaction to the course pack with a particular focus on writing an academic essay, punctuation, American and British English plagiarism, and style guide.

a) Writing Academic Essay

The first chapter of the coursepack provided me with an important concept, including the need to define and analyze the question and task, research the topic by using credible academic sources, develop an essay plan to properly answer the question and determine the type of information to use, and describes how to organize ideas, draft, edit, and produce an academic essay (EUCLID 2021, 7).

This chapter also provides important rule of thumb for writing an academic paper, which includes the need to state the main thesis at the beginning of the paper, stay focused on the main idea, avoid sweeping generalities, write clearly, support assertions, consider alternative, opposing explanations and ideas, among others essay (EUCLID 2021, 9).

While reading this section, I felt that the course pack could be further improved by incorporating issues such as argumentative, expository, narrative, and descriptive writing and by making it much more specific to international academic writing in public health.

b) Punctuation

The second chapter of the course pack provided an important description of punctuation marks and examples of their use, including the use of the apostrophe, brackets, bullet points, colons, semicolons, commas, dashes and hyphens, ellipsis, full stops, exclamation marks, question mark, and quotation marks essay (EUCLID 2021, 16-23). This section gave me an essential lesson on correct use of punctuation to add clarity and precision to my writing and provide emphasis to certain parts of the sentence. I liked the examples that show common mistakes in using punctuation.

c) American and British English

The third chapter of the coursepack focused on American and British English and provided examples of differences in pronunciation, spelling, meaning, grammar, punctuation, usage, and other aspects (EUCLID 2021, 15-27) . I was aware of the existence of some differences between American and British English. However, I never expected too much difference in pronunciation, spelling, meaning, grammar, usage, and other aspects until I read the course material. As a non-native speaker of English, I was overwhelmed by too many differences and faced with the challenge of differentiating which one is which (American or British). In my country Ethiopia the medium of instruction in schools and

universities is British English, but almost all the books and computers are from America which resulted mixed use of American and British English.

d) Plagiarism

Chapter four of the coursepack defines plagiarism as the use of a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information and describes the need to give credit to the author " When using any quote, paraphrase, statistic/data, or visuals (such as a graph) that is borrowed from another source." (EUCLID 2021, 34) This chapter also describes how to cite sources of information properly.

Plagiarism includes citing incorrect information about a source, reusing own previous work without citing the previous work, and theft of other people's work. Plagiarism can be avoided by being honest while writing, including by being original, using own words in paraphrasing, always citing the source of the idea, text, or illustration, enclosing copied verbatim from another source within quotation marks, and proper reference to the source of information.

The course pack provided me good knowledge on proper citation, quotation, and paraphrasing and the need not to cite common knowledge that can be found in numerous areas (EUCLID 2021, 35-37).

e) Style Guide

Chapter five of the coursepack helped me to understand that writing is much more than just the correct usage of punctuation, grammar, and vocabulary and includes the length of sentences, the layout of the manuscript, structure, and use of font, spelling, abbreviations, terminology, and symbols, among others. This chapter emphasized the need to ensure a consistent writing style and strictly follow the style guide for publications or written materials produced by many contributing authors to produce coherent and consistent written material (EUCLID 2021, 41-42). This reminded me of my challenge with colleagues in producing materials involving many contributors.

3) CONCLUSION

The course pack provided me good understanding of academic and professional writing, proper use of punctuation marks, American and British English, plagiarism, writing style, and Chicago style. I found the course pack very important not only for my study but also for my work - which includes drafting policy and strategy documents, plans, training materials, guidelines, protocols, reports, presentations, and various tools in the field of public health.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *How to write a Response Paper*. Bangui: Euclid University.

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